

Exploring Tipping Points and Their
Impacts Using Earth System Models

TipESM Exploitation Strategy

Deliverable D9.4

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

About this document

Actual Submission Date: 26 February 2025

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Work package: WP9 Dissemination, Communication, Clustering, Project, and Data Management

Authors:

Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), PP1, Justyna Bekier jabe@dm.dk

Contributing authors:

Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), PP1, Erika Hayashi, erh@dm.dk

Met Office (METO), PP8, Hazel Jeffery, hazel.jeffery@metoffice.gov.uk

Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI), PP2, Nikki Brown, nicola.brown@smhi.se

Reviewer:

Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), PP1, Chiara Bearzotti chb@dm.dk

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of contents

1. Introduction	4
1.1 Purpose of the Exploitation Strategy	4
1.2 Scope of the Exploitation Strategy	5
2. Exploitation in TipESM	5
3. Overview of Key Exploitable Results	6
4. Exploitation Pathways for TipESM Results	7
4.1 Strategy for results uptake by operational users	10
4.2 Strategy for results uptake by policy users	14
4.3 Strategy for results uptake by citizens and broader society	16
4.4 Strategy for results uptake by scientific users	16
5. Knowledge management, protection and exploitation of results and Intellectual Property	17
5.1 Requirements set by the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement	17
5.2 The IP and Innovation Management System	18
6. Updates of the Exploitation Strategy	20
7. Contribution to the TipESM objectives	22
8. References	22

1. Introduction

TipESM brings together scientists from a range of disciplines to deliver a step change in our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on ecosystems and society, combined with a set of early warning indicators and safe future emission pathways that minimise the risk of exceeding such tipping points.

This document is an Exploitation Strategy, outlining how TipESM will work to ensure the relevance, uptake and usability of project results so that they live on beyond the project duration. Owners of key project results will rely on this strategy to effectively disseminate and allow the exploitation of these results.

The document starts with outlining the purpose and scope of the Exploitation Strategy, followed by a definition of Exploitation used in TipESM. Next, an overview of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) is presented, as well as the exploitation pathways designed to reach different target audiences. Lastly, this document outlines how the requirements set by the project Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement related to knowledge management, protection and exploitation of results and Intellectual Property have explicitly been set up in this project.

1.1 Purpose of the Exploitation Strategy

TipESM expects the project results to be exploited (such as data, methods, and protocols as well as scientific knowledge and knowledge essential to policy and society) through further research, policymaking, and educational activities, other than those addressed in the project. Additionally, we aim for the results to inform climate- and weather operational services. The purpose of this Exploitation Strategy is to identify potential users of the TipESM's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and propose pathways for the successful uptake of project results among these users.

To ensure a broad and effective uptake of results beyond the project, TipESM will:

1. Ensure that the project results are broadly accessible, meeting Open Science/Open Access commitments and following FAIR principles—findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and

- Reusability of research data. Information on compliance with Open Access and Open Science requirements is explained in the data management plan and will not be repeated in this document.
2. Maintain dialogue with identified target users and engage them in co-creation to make the project outputs relevant and usable, and to increase the chances of their uptake.
 3. Reach broader audiences through tailored communication and dissemination activities.

1.2 Scope of the Exploitation Strategy

This exploitation strategy is a living document that will be updated throughout the project's lifetime, culminating in a final report on communication, dissemination, and exploitation that will include recommendations beyond the project. This first version focuses on the pathways for engagement with target users to ensure the uptake of TipESM results, describing the envisioned exploitation process. As we continuously engage in dialogue with our target users, the next version of the exploitation strategy will provide an update on these discussions. Updates will be provided with the periodic reports.

2. Exploitation in TipESM

According to the Grant Agreement Annex 5 Specific Rules on IPR, "exploitation" is the use of results in further innovation and deployment activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including, among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities. TipESM partners will - up to four years after the end of the action - use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing.

Exploitation can also be non-commercial, for example, linked to the use in non-commercial research or non-commercial teaching activities. Given the project scope, TipESM does not engage in product development, and commercial exploitation potential is limited. The results of TipESM are expected to be of scientific, societal, and policy relevance, e.g. used to influence R&I policy or decision-making. Publishing results in the Horizon Results Platform ensures high visibility to a variety of potential users and stakeholders including industry, academia, investors, and public administrations, and may lead to finding help to exploit the results directly (e.g. financing) or finding third parties which may be interested in exploiting the results.

3. Overview of Key Exploitable Results

There are four categories of Key Exploitable Results (KER) produced in TipESM as indicated in the original description of the action: (1) Data, tools, and applications, (2) Knowledge for policy and society, (3) Methods/protocols, and (4) Scientific knowledge (see Table 1 for examples).

Type of KER	Key Exploitable Results
Data, tools, and applications	Ensemble of Earth system model (ESM) simulations to explore tipping points (TPs). Output from TipESM made available on the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF). TP risk register. Interactive mapping system with geographical impacts of climate TPs on ecosystem and society. A register of Early Warning Indicators for climate and ecological TPs, including guidance for future observation networks. Updated catalogue TPs and tipping cascades in the Earth system. Datasets on hazard exposure for tipping in social systems.
Knowledge for policy and society	Policy briefs and insights summarizing the latest knowledge on TPs and their impacts. A report on climate thresholds that lead to tipping in ecological and social systems; Lessons learned in ESM modelling. Transdisciplinary approaches in EU projects. Synthesis of tipping elements and thresholds across terrestrial and marine ecosystems. Policy workshops on the risk and potential consequences of crossing climate TPs. Online tutorial explaining TPs to e.g. school students (16 to 18-year old) linked to their curriculum.
Methods / protocols	Protocol for coupled ESM simulations for TIPMIP - Tipping Point Modelling Intercomparison Project - and realization of these experiments with the project ESMs. Techniques for triggering climate TPs in ESMs (e.g. so-called "What-If" scenarios). Integration of climate impact models with observations to identify tipping in ecological and social systems. Improved integration of Earth system and climate impact modelling.

Scientific knowledge	Scientific publications and deliverables of interest for exploitation by other scientists or experts from diverse disciplines contributing to the project.
----------------------	--

The exploitation of these results is closely linked to the planned dissemination and communication activities (see the deliverable D9.2 TipESM Communication and Dissemination Strategy¹) to ensure the results reach and have successful uptake among the identified target audiences. Beyond these activities, we focus on co-creation processes with selected audiences, ensuring the value and usability of the results.

4. Exploitation Pathways for TipESM Results

The exploitation pathways for each type of KER consists of three key elements:

- Identified project deliverables and milestones, with which the KER is achieved and made available to the users.
- Identified primary target users for each type of KER.
- Identified strategies to engage with the primary target user groups.

Key pathways to exploitation are included in this initial draft of the exploitation plan. The following table provides an overview of the exploitation pathways for each KER type.

Type of KER	Examples of KERs	Corresponding Deliverables (D) /Milestones (M)	Primary target users	Strategy
Data, tools, and applications	Ensemble of Earth System Models (ESM) simulations to explore tipping points (TPs). Output from TipESM available on the Earth	D1.3 TipESM Simulation data for TIPMIP.	Operational users (e.g., climate services, disaster management bodies,	Strategy for results uptake by operational users (§ 4.1).

¹ Bekier, J. & Hayashi, E. (2024). D9.2 TipESM Communication and Dissemination Strategy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12180244>

Type of KER	Examples of KERs	Corresponding Deliverables (D) /Milestones (M)	Primary target users	Strategy
	System Grid Federation (ESGF).		observational agencies).	
	TP risk register.	D8.2 Synthesis report on risk analysis of TPs.		
	Interactive mapping system with geographical impacts of climate TPs on ecosystem and society.	D7.3 Interactive mapping system with geographical impacts of climate TPs.		
	A register of Early Warning Indicators for climate and ecological TPs, including guidance for future observation networks.	D4.1 Register of Early Warning Indicators.		
	Updated catalogue TPs and tipping cascades in the Earth system.	D2.1 Catalogue of TPs found in ESM simulations; D5.1 Interactions between TPs.		
	Datasets on hazard exposure for tipping in social systems.	D7.2 Report on societal and ecosystem effects of climate TPs.		
Knowledge for policy	Policy briefs and insights summarizing the latest knowledge on TPs and their impacts.	D9.7 Policy briefing nr. 1, D10.2 Policy briefing nr. 2.	Policy users, e.g., European Commission officers, European	Strategy for results uptake by policy users (§ 4.2).

Type of KER	Examples of KERs	Corresponding Deliverables (D) /Milestones (M)	Primary target users	Strategy
	A report on climate thresholds that lead to tipping in ecological and social systems.	D7.2 Report on the societal and ecosystem effects of climate TPs.	Parliament, government agencies on national and regional levels; and climate advisors.	
	Lessons learned in ESM modelling. Transdisciplinary approaches in EU projects.	Communicated through different channels.		
	Synthesis of tipping elements and thresholds across terrestrial and marine ecosystems.	D6.2 Report on tipping in terrestrial ecosystems; D6.3 Report on tipping in marine ecosystems.	International assessments such as IPCC, IPBES and UNFCCC.	
	Policy workshops on the risk and potential consequences of crossing climate TPs.	D9.7 Policy briefing nr. 1, D10.2 Policy briefing nr. 2.		
Knowledge for society	Online tutorial explaining TPs to e.g. school students (16 to 18-year old) linked to their curriculum.	Developed and promoted through different channels.	Citizens and broader society (e.g. students).	Strategy for results uptake by operational users (§ 4.3).

Type of KER	Examples of KERs	Corresponding Deliverables (D) /Milestones (M)	Primary target users	Strategy
Methods / protocols	Protocol for coupled ESM simulations for TIPMIP and realization of these experiments with the project ESMs.	D1.1 TipESM experiment protocol for TIPMIP.	Climate modelling and impact modelling communities.	Strategy for results uptake by scientific users (§ 4.4).
	Techniques for triggering climate TPs in ESMs (e.g. so-called “What-If” scenarios).	D1.2 Triggering tipping events in coupled ESMs.		
	Integration of climate impact models with observations to identify tipping in ecological and social systems.	Developed throughout the project; no specific deliverables or milestones are linked to this type of KER.		
	Improved integration of Earth system and climate impact modelling.	D1.3 TipESM simulation data for TIPMIP.		
Scientific knowledge	Scientific publications.	As developed throughout the project, there are no specific deliverables or milestones linked to this type of KER.	Climate science and social science research communities.	Strategy for results uptake by scientific users (§ 4.4).
	Results of interest for exploitation by other scientists or experts from diverse disciplines contributing to the project.			

4.1 Strategy for results uptake by operational users

With the term “operational users,” we refer to users interested in climate-related information, tools, and applications for managing climate risks and opportunities in various sectors. These can include a variety of climate or weather services, e.g., related to agriculture, water management, urban planning, transport, health, or disaster risk reduction.

The goal is to evaluate, together with the users, the relevance of specific TipESM results, the challenges and opportunities related to their uptake, and potential improvements in terms of the delivery format of these results.

A two-fold strategy will be pursued here:

1. **Network of Operational Users:** In TipESM, the project partners have strong connections to climate and weather operational services, not least through the meteorological agencies that are partners of the project (e.g., Danish Meteorological Institute, Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, the UK Met Office, the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute) and Meteo France, one of the external collaborators of TipESM. Building on this network, TipESM will ensure that these operational users take advantage of the key exploitable results.
2. **Copernicus Climate Change Services (C3S):** C3S provides climate data and information on impacts on a range of topics and [sectoral areas](#) through the [Climate Data Store \(CDS\)](#). The CDS is designed to enable users to tailor services to more specific public or commercial needs. The C3S work complements the established range of meteorological and environmental services that each European country already has in place. C3S also involves the national climate service providers as well as relevant academic communities in the implementation of C3S. Engaging with C3S is crucial to ensure the long-term uptake of TipESM results.

Potential contents

- Key “operational” outputs, such as the risk register of tipping points, the register of Early Warning Indicators, or the catalogue of tipping points and cascading effects between them.
- Ensemble of ESM simulations to explore tipping points. TipESM outputs are available in the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF).
- Interactive mapping system with geographical impacts of climate TPs on ecosystem and society.

- Datasets on hazard exposure for tipping in social systems.
- Results of the showcases for replications (see the example below).

Formats for uptake

- Workshops to test and validate project outputs (“showcases”) with relevant climate services at the national level in the countries covered by TipESM partners: The Danish Meteorological Institute implemented a showcase of this strategy to test its usefulness. A description of the showcase can be found below.
- Ongoing dialogue with target users e.g., services in meteorological offices and weather services.
- Information delivered to the Copernicus Climate Change Services ([C3S](#)) [meetings](#), [workshops](#), and [training](#) to users of the C3S Climate Data Store (CDS).

Showcase for replication

As part of building an exploitation strategy, the coordination team of TipESM explored a scenario of developing a link between TipESM and climate services within the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI). A showcase of how such a scenario can work in practice was conducted to verify the possibility of translating a similar approach in other meteorological offices, starting with KNMI, SMHI, and Met Office as partners in TipESM. The co-creation strategy and lessons learned from the showcase and further implementation of this scenario will be shared in the form of guidelines to enable transferability to other national meteorological and weather services.

DMI workshop with the Danish Klimaatlas

In 2024, DMI organised an internal workshop to identify the most relevant KERs for the Danish Klimaatlas, a Danish climate service developed and provided by DMI.

The Danish Klimaatlas <https://www.dmi.dk/klima-atlas/introduction-to-klimaatlas> provides data on municipality, drainage basin and coastal stretch levels showing future changes in temperature, precipitation, extreme precipitation, relative sea level and storm surge heights. It thereby gives an indication of areas with a particular future risk of being impacted by extremes. The tool provides fundamental climate data so municipalities can take the necessary precautions and guard citizens, infrastructure and buildings against the expected extreme weather in the future.

The workshop was hosted by the TipESM project office (including the Project Coordinator and Project Managers), with representatives of the Danish Klimaatlas project as participants. It started with a brief presentation of TipESM and an introduction to the project's KERs. This was followed by an exercise in which Klimaatlas team members selected the KERs most relevant to their own work.

Once the 1-3 key KERs were identified, the workshop continued to uncover the following information:

- **Baseline/Existing service:** Identify existing tools/services that serve a similar purpose. What's already in place? What works well, and what doesn't?
- **Gaps/challenges:** What are the key challenges or missing pieces in existing services? How might TipESM results address these?
- **Uptake Scenario:** Where can you imagine this KER being taken up?
- **Added value/benefits:** How can TipESM results provide added value? What benefits do they bring to Danish Klimaatlas users?
- **Needs/wishes:** What is missing in TipESM results to meet operational needs? What additional features or data would be ideal?
- **Uptake challenges:** What barriers exist to adopting TipESM results? E.g., technical, operational, financial, or user acceptance issues.

In the dialogue with the Danish Klimaatlas team, the TipESM team received the following feedback related to the exploitation of project results among municipality-related climate services:

- Municipalities work with data relevant to them in terms of adaptation on a local scale. Thus, it would be essential to understand the teleconnections between global events like tipping points (e.g. Amazon dieback) and local impacts (e.g. average temperatures in the municipality).
- The climate services rely on IPCC reports as a source of information; contributing timely and relevant research to IPCC reports would help ensure the long-term exploitation of project results. This is already incorporated into TipESM's ambitions and target audiences.
- Communicating the knowledge of tipping points impacts through storylines would be a welcome contribution to municipal climate services. This is also in line with TipESM long-term plans, where storylines are considered an appropriate strategy to support the communication and exploitation of the risk register. In line with this, a storyline workshop will be conducted during the upcoming TipESM Annual Event in 2025.

The workshop showcased how TipESM can engage with target audiences and receive feedback on the usability of project KERs. At DMI, the dialogue with Klimaatlas will continue, while this workshop example will be shared with other KER owners in TipESM as a model for replication.

4.2 Strategy for results uptake by policy users

Policy users refer to the target audience that can adopt TipESM results and integrate the knowledge created in the project into policymaking at various levels.

This audience includes:

- European Commission officers, European Parliament.
- IPCC, IPBES, and UNFCCC.
- Government agencies on national levels, and climate advisors in these agencies.

To ensure relevance and a suitable format for policy uptake, TipESM aims to engage with policymakers throughout the project—not just through dedicated policy briefings (linked to D9.7 Policy briefing nr. 1 and D10.2 Policy briefing nr. 2) but through broader activities, transferring the knowledge and results from the project in a way that is useful and convenient to policy users. An ongoing dialogue with them will help in achieving this.

Engagement in policy events and continuous dialogue with policy stakeholders provides essential opportunities for feedback and to increase the visibility of TipESM project results in the policy arena.

Additionally, through the network of project partners, TipESM engages in dialogue with climate advisors to national ministries (in the countries covered by the partners who are national meteorological services) to ensure local dissemination of knowledge and results.

In the project, a Stakeholder Reference Group will be established and consulted for co-production and co-design of policy recommendations, as well as validation and feedback, to ensure that the knowledge gained from the project is actionable for the policy users.

Potential contents:

- Key project results are presented in a short and easily digestible format.

- Policy-relevant scientific knowledge, developed and delivered in coordination and by clustering with other EU projects, e.g., ClimTip and OptimESM, and with other international initiatives and communities, e.g., TIPMIP.

Formats for uptake:

- Speaking engagements for instance at ECCA conferences, policy briefings, side events to COP or similar, policy roundtables, and Knowledge4policy events.
- Written materials such as summaries of technical articles, policy briefs, as well as factsheets and infographics.
- Linking with online channels and platforms such as the EEA Climate-Adapt platform, or the Horizon Results Platform.
- Direct engagement and dialogue with climate advisors to national ministries (e.g., via meteorological services represented in the project).
- Clustering with projects to ensure streamlined communication to policymakers.

To date, TipESM has participated in the following policy events:

- **October 10, 2024: CINEA policy briefing.** TipESM participated in a clustering event hosted by The European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) together with the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) for projects in Cluster 5 Destination 1. The event aimed at conveying policy-relevant messages from the projects to EC staff and policy officers. Projects offered their latest scientific knowledge in support of Conference of the Parties (COP) preparation and the climate policy agenda of the European Union. TipESM was selected to present under the theme “Nationally Determined Contributions” (NDCs) ambition, long-term strategies and implementation of climate action”. The discussions and Q&A provided important feedback for TipESM on presenting its results for uptake among policy users.
- **November 5, 2024: Joint Research Center (JRC) tipping points policy event.** TipESM participated in a two-day scientific workshop on “Raising Awareness of Tipping Points: Implications for EU Governance”. The event aimed to present state-of-the-art scientific

developments and engage policymakers in dialogue on the need for better-informed risk assessments of tipping points. Proactive strategies and policies for responding to emerging threats were also discussed.

4.3 Strategy for results uptake by citizens and broader society

Citizens and the broader society are identified as another target user group for whom the uptake of knowledge from TipESM will be significant. To that end, the exploitation plan of TipESM assumes the development of robust knowledge translated into usable and practical materials that can be adopted by the broader society. Here, particular attention will be given to educating young people through engagement with youth action groups and schools.

Potential contents:

- Key project results are presented in a short and easily digestible format.
- Summaries for a lay audience of key information about tipping point precursors, drivers and impacts.
- Summaries of the key discussion points on the risks of tipping points.
- Summaries of the key recommendations for immediate climate- and adaptation action.

Formats for uptake:

- Information materials (digital and printed).
- Dialogue at various speaking engagements e.g. science fairs, public lectures, or panel discussions.
- Posts in online channels such as the TipESM website, LinkedIn posts, YouTube videos, and the project newsletter. Features in magazines and newspapers.
- Webinars, inputs to teaching modules, including online tutorials explaining TPs to e.g. school students (16 to 18-year old) linked to their curriculum.

4.4 Strategy for results uptake by scientific users

Scientific users, including the climate modelling and research communities, represent another vital target user group for the uptake of project results. The scientific users are already closely linked to the project

community, and continuously engaged with through publications, conferences, and personal dialogue. TipESM will also reach out to connected scientific communities looking at the impacts of Tipping Points from the social sciences point of view.

Potential contents:

- New research outputs such as publications.
- New methods, approaches and experiment protocols to study tipping points.

Formats for uptake:

- Ad hoc engagement with TIPMIP and CMIP, direct dialogue with the climate modelling community.
- Direct dialogue with impact modelling community (models planned to be used in TipESM include BIOME4, ISIMIP3, JULES-ES, LPJ-GUESS, ECO-Spillv.1.2, VIC3+ELEVMal, HBM, ORCHIDEE, and SAER).
- Participation and organisation of conferences, symposia, workshops, and trainings.
- Publications in Open Access scientific journals.

5. Knowledge management, protection and exploitation of results and Intellectual Property

5.1 Requirements set by the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement

In the Consortium Agreement (CA), the partners have already regulated how access rights, background, results free from restrictions, ownership of results, protection of results, exploitation of results, transfer and licensing, and innovation management will be managed. This document, together with the provisions of the Grant Agreement provides the backbone of the exploitation strategy.

Organisations and individuals outside the consortium will also benefit from our results, given the requirement to share results in open access, as indicated in the data management plan.

Exploitation (or use) will be pursued **through research activities, skills and educational training, and policy making**. It is not foreseen to pursue commercial activities in this project, given the scope/nature of its activities and expected results. It has been agreed that each partner takes measures to ensure 'exploitation' of its results by:

- using them in further research activities (outside the action);
- developing, creating or marketing a product or process.

As a general obligation, TipESM partners must — up to four years after the end of the action — use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing.

The Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) provide a framework for exploiting intellectual property and underpin how we promote innovation, encourage invention and creativity, and thereby help society to benefit from the generated intellectual property. IP Ownership Results are owned by the beneficiaries that generate them.

5.2 The IP and Innovation Management System

The consortium has agreed on an **innovation management system** relying on the following implementation steps which correspond to activities under the lead of specific actors in the project governance structure. Innovation Management (EC Definition) is the “overall management of all activities related to understanding needs, to successfully identify new ideas, and managing them, to develop new products and services which satisfy these needs.”

The following steps are implemented:

1. Securing the foundations
2. Proactive monitoring of the project results/outputs
3. Management and protection of the project results/outputs
4. Dissemination of the project results according to the scheduled plan

Step 1: Securing the foundations

Lead: This task is implemented by the Coordination, including the Project Office, supported by the Steering Committee and the legal representatives of each partner organisation (including associated partners).

Description of the tasks: In the Consortium Agreement, each partner has identified the background brought into the project and agreed on rules for IP and innovation management.

Additional rules have been set for:

- Joint ownership
- Transfer of Results
- Dissemination of Own Results
- Cooperation obligations
- Licensing
- Access Rights: Background, accessing rights for implementation, accessing rights for exploitation
- Protection of Results.

In line with the consortium agreement, the ownership of the TipESM results is **joint**. This means that each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned results for non-commercial research, teaching activities and public task duties on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owners. Each of the joint owners is entitled to exploit the jointly owned results otherwise and to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties (without any right to sub-license) if the other joint owners are given at least 45 calendar days advance notice; and fair and reasonable conditions. The joint owners shall agree on all protection measures and the division of related costs in advance. TipESM partners also adequately protect their results for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage. If intellectual property protection is possible and justified, it will take into account all relevant considerations, including the prospects for commercial exploitation, legitimate interests of the other beneficiaries and any other legitimate interests.

Step 2: Proactive monitoring of the project results

Lead: This task is implemented by WP leads and co-leads and the Project Office.

Description of the task: Proactive monitoring of research outputs - regular reviews within the work packages and across the work packages for identifying all relevant IPs such as software, codes, papers, know-how, etc. and shared results.

The Project Office, supported by partner ETT, will ensure that the open science obligations set by Horizon Europe and the requirements of the Data Management Plan are complied with.

Step 3: Management and protection of the project results

Lead: This task is implemented by the project partners' legal advisors and the researchers they employ. The Project Office supports the process.

Description of the task: If and as soon as IP emerges, clarify ownership in compliance with the clauses of the consortium agreement. Staff involved in this step will check for “hidden traps” (publications, posters, etc.), which might affect potential IP protection measures and potential patentability. The Project Office will ensure that the open science obligations set by Horizon Europe and the requirements of the Data Management Plan are complied with.

Step 4: Dissemination of the project outputs according to the planned schedule

Lead: The coordination and Steering Committee, together with the individual scientists involved, implement this task. The Project Office supports the process.

Description of the tasks: Regular dissemination activity, regular record keeping at the project level, and monitoring of the impacts.

6. Updates of the Exploitation Strategy

The exploitation strategy will be regularly updated during the entire project. Updates will be submitted to the European Commission as an integral part of the Project Periodic Reports, as stipulated in the Grant Agreement. Updates of the present plan will also be highlighted in the Project Periodic Reports. In the final stages of the project (M36-48), best practices in capturing and assessing the Intellectual Property and providing measures for exploitation will be provided to the consortium.

The exploitation strategy will evolve during the project and be updated halfway through with a report on exploitation activities. At the end, the plan will be consolidated to draw up the *final exploitation plans for the project legacy, in line with the requirements of the consortium agreement*.

The Project Office will oversee the completion of the Results Ownership List (ROL) in the final periodic report, including input from all relevant partners. The last version of the plan before the end of the project must include the dissemination and exploitation activities that the beneficiaries plan to implement in a period of up to 4 years after the end of the project. During that period, TipESM will continue reporting on the progress of their activities and the project results through the European Commission Continuous Reporting tool, which will remain accessible. After the project's closure, IPR provisions will remain in force, as defined in the CA.

The consortium will also consider the [Horizon Results Platform](#) to share key exploitable results (KER, high potential to be exploited, i.e. to be used in a product, process or service, or act as an essential input to further research, R&I-related policy or education, etc). The Horizon Results Platform (HRP) is a platform developed by the European Commission to help promote the exploitation of the results from the R&I framework programmes. It enables beneficiaries of grants from Horizon Europe to publish and promote the uptake of their results towards their target audiences. It can be accessed by the partners through the Portal.

Publishing results in the Horizon Results Platform ensures high visibility to a variety of potential users and stakeholders, including industry, academia, investors, public administrations, etc., and may lead to finding help to exploit the results directly (e.g., financing) or finding third parties interested in exploiting the results.

If key exploitable results are not exploited one year after the end of the action, the use of the Horizon Results Platform becomes mandatory for TipESM partners. In this context, the coordinator will use the Results Ownership List (ROL) to cross-check which KERs must be uploaded to the Horizon Results Platform.

The project has successfully become an early adopter of the [EU Open Research Repository Pilot](#). This has enabled TipESM the following:

- Share and preserve all the research outputs in a single trusted repository.
- All submissions will be immediately indexed in the EU Open Research Repository.
- Integration with OpenAIRE to facilitate reporting in the EC Participant Portal.
- Gain visibility and impact for the project by grouping all outputs and making them easy to find and cite.
- Measure usage statistics (views/downloads) of TipESM records, as well as citations.
- Ensure compliance with the related open science requirements in the Horizon Europe grant agreement.
- Manage research data in line with the FAIR principles.

Depending on the scope of the results, the project will also consider applying for dissemination and exploitation support services, and IP management services provided by the European Commission, during and after the end of your action i.e. to apply for the [Horizon Booster](#):

<https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

7. Contribution to the TipESM objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following project objective SO9.

<p>SO9</p>	<p><i>To provide policy guidance to the EC, IPCC, IPBES and the UNFCCC Global Stocktake, on the likelihood and consequences of crossing climate TPs and mitigation options to minimise the chance of such events. KPIs: A summary of the leading project findings for non-specialists and leaflets highlighting potential impacts on a) human systems and society b) ecosystems and biodiversity. Deliverables: D9.2, D9.4, D9.5, D9.7, D10.1 and D10.2.</i></p> <p>This deliverable provides a plan for the exploitation of project results by different target groups. It outlines how the project will ensure that its results are relevant and usable also for institutions like the European Commission and global assessments like IPCC, IPBES and UNFCCC.</p>	<p>1-8, 9,10</p>
------------	--	------------------

8. References

European Commission: European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Your guide to intellectual property management in Horizon Europe, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022,

<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/409260>

European Commission: European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Scherer, J., Weber, S., Alveen, P., Sweeney, E. et al., European IP Helpdesk – Successful valorisation of knowledge and research results in Horizon Europe – Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022,

<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/437645>

Horizon Europe Programme Guide:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

Horizon Europe Annotated Model Grant Agreement

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

European IP Helpdesk Virtual Training Session: Dissemination and Exploitation in Horizon Europe

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gyXIYDkXQ2E>

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Valorisation policies – Making research results work for society – Industry-academia collaboration, Publications Office, 2021,

<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/573275>

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Research & innovation valorisation channels and tools – Boosting the transformation of knowledge into new sustainable solutions, Publications Office, 2020,

<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/480584>

Factsheet: Making Results Work for Society

https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/18557006-791b-4252-a78a-a2db82693155_en?filename=ec_rtd_valorisation_factsheet.pdf